

Muslim Attitude toward Women Education Current Scenario

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: October

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Ambreen. "Muslim Attitude toward Women Education Current Scenario." *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 83–87.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3549254>

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Abstract

In the current scenario women issues have been acquired great importance all over the world, reason is obvious. For long time the women were kept in total subjugation in all patriarchal societies. Now, regarding the position of women and their rights discussed all over the world. The girl-child education has been a burning and continues issue in the developing countries of which India is one. In the pre Islamic period, women had lost all the rights in Arabia. The birth of a girl was considered ominous. Not all but most of the tribes of Arab was engaged in the infanticide of females, her birth was not an occasion of rejoicing but humiliation. The Muslim women have been treated as men's equal rights on the consideration of their nature and behaviours from the rise of Islam. Islam frequently uplifts the status and rights of women and gave exceptional consideration on their education. The significance of education can be judged by the first revelation of the Holy Book. The first revealed word "Iqra" is a command that means "read" and that includes the ideas of "learning", "exploring" and "Seeking education". Allah has created human being with indefinite talents and merits and has instructed for developing these talents through seeking education.

This paper investigates various aspects of women education in the time of prophet as well as modern times in the light of Quran and Hadith without gender discrimination.

Keywords: Islamic perspective, Women's Education, Current scenario.

Introduction

In 19th century, "the Europeans dominated many religion of the world, i.e. Britain in India and Africa, Russia in Central Asia and Holland in Southeast Asia. At that time, many reform movements in several countries such as Egypt and India, led by Jamal al-Din al- Afghani (1838-1897) and Sir Syed Ahmad Khan (1817- 1898) respectively. They saw the need for serious reform. The religious reforms needed to be designed to suit the needs of modern realities.

Now i age of globalization, and industrialization has altered the image of Muslim women. Education became a pre-requisite for playing many of the modern roles. In turn education also awakened Muslim women to a sense of their own self-importance and this encouraged them to assert many of the lights which were denied to them.

Women Rights in Islam

The problem of the position and role of the women in Islam is still alive in modern Muslim societies. “There has been a lot of confusion and misunderstanding on women’s involvement in public affairs in most of the Islamic world. But, Islam was the first religion which talked about rights of women. It endorsed daughter’s share in fathers’ property, wives share in husband’s earnings and responsibilities of husband towards wives. For the earliest time a human cure and legal status was given to women. Women were allowed to work, subject to certain condition. Thus compared to pre-Islamic position of women, Islamic legislation meant an enormous progress, the woman has the right to administer wealth she has brought into the family or has earned by her own work. As Qur’an mentioned that:

“And when the news of (the birth of) female (child) is brought to any of them his face become dark and he is filled with inward grief!” (16:58)

It was the first time a human treatment and legal status was given to women. Women were also allowed to work, subject to certain condition. Thus compared to pre-Islamic position of women, Islamic legislation meant an all-round progress for women where they had the right to work and earn and spend the earning in a way they thought best for it. Qur’an says:

“He created you from a single soul” (4:1)

Education is the major and birth right of every human being (Muslim and Muslimah). Because of male female are children of the same parents, for that reason they should be treated equally in all respect and should be provided equal rights whether educational or social. Islam puts considerable emphasise on its followers The importance of gaining and education has been continually emphasized in the Qur’an and hadith, which are the significant sources of direction for Muslims. Women found almost half of population of every society and the idea of treating them as less important does not survive in the Muslim society. But unfortunately, due to the weakness of Muslims against the hostile propaganda of opposition to Islam, the exact stand of Islam towards female education is distracted.

In the verses of the holy Qur’an, women have been directed to follow certain principles of Islam. However, it become essential for women to educate herself in order to understand and follow the principles in letter and spirit. She has been categorically instructed to obey the Holy Prophet this commandment made women to think and seek the knowledge of Islamic teachings. The Muslim women practised the principles of Islam and acquired honourable status in the society. Hazrat Ayesha (RA) says:

“The Ansar women were wonderful! Nothing could check them from understanding of Islam”. (Muslim)

Qur’anic Interpretation on Women Education

The first verse of the Quran to be revealed to the prophet Mohammad indicates the important of education in Islam; the verse started with the word “Iqra” is a command that means “read” in Arabic, and that implies the concept of “learning”, “exploring” and “Seeking education”. This demonstrates that reading is the way to approach the creator of all that exists. Allah has created human being with indefinite talents and merits and has instructed for developing these talents through seeking education. Acquirement of knowledge (‘ilm) is stressed in Islam as a significant action besides its dissemination. It has been made obligatory (fard) upon its believers, irrespective of gender, to learn and broadcast knowledge. Prophet Muhammad himself emphasised on women education, Said:

“Seeking knowledge is compulsory for each and every Muslims”

There is no verse in the Qur’an that directly or indirectly places the education of males over

women; but, Fatwas or legal opinions are still issued by some ulama or religious scholars prohibiting women from participation in the workforce.

Prophetic Methodology for Women Education

The Holy prophet himself was a teacher, he taught the Qur'an to companions and explained the significance of the Qur'anic verses and guided them to lead the life of true Muslim according to the behest of the Qur'an. Islam regularly forms right of girl in respect of all areas and confirmed honour and self-respect as similar male child nevertheless of gender discrimination. Education of girl's is highlighted in several of Al-Hadiths. The Prophet Muhammad said,

“Whoever has three daughters, or three sisters, or two daughters, or two sisters and he keeps good company with them and fears Allah regarding them, then Paradise is for him.” .

The wives of the Prophet took maintenance of the education of the girls'. The Companions took attention of the education of their child. This was reported by Abu Musa Al-Ashari that,

The Prophet said: “He who has a slave –girl and teaches her good manners and improves her education and then manumits and marries her, will get a double reward.” .

Therefore, girls' education is most significant matter without observation of discrimination among children. The Prophet also produced different vigorous method for how to be educated. Throughout the Islamic history women made great contribution to the cause of education and learning. They became the source of guidance and enlightenment for the society.

Present Scenario

Data demonstration of the Girl (women) living in the Muslim inhabited zones that have formal education as well as the Islamic education is low. This is due to numerous reasons, which consist socio-economic aspects, deprived knowledge of the religious understanding, and over-all methodology of the people together with the Girl. The common belief of the Girl or women is that her knowledge is end in kitchen as assumed by the generality of the society. So that, when she is sent to school, she does not take it serious. The female Muslim needs to change her attitude towards education. She should take hers studies serious so that she can be useful to herself as well as to the society. The story of Fatima (RA), the daughter of our noble Prophet is an example of a house wife who made a lot of sacrifice to obtain her husband's pleasure who every Muslim female must emulate.

Need for Women Education

Women empowerment can only be through the provision of adequate and functional education to women folk. The quality of education being advocated by women to the girl-child is that type of education which embarrassed the spirit of self-realization and all that are needed for the countries development like mass literacy, economic empowerment etc. Women are struggling to improve their status through girl-child education which entails the of challenging access to formal education. This is based on the premise that; education has been judged to be a viable instrument of social change.

Educated women in the society have recommended that the future aspirations of girl -child as cited in the spirit of universal basic Education (UBE), provision of formal and non-formal education is needed for women folk because:

1. It would authorize them to know and agitate for their rights to education, healthiness, housing, food, clothing etc.
2. It would authorize them to fight against every form of discrimination against their folk, assert themselves about their right to equal behaviour with their male counterparts as bonafide citizens of this country.

3. It would enable the women take decision and accept responsibilities for taking such a decision concerning them.
4. It would give economic power to the women by enabling them to contribute their quota to the economic growth of the nation. And also empower scientifically and technologically.

It would help them to decrease maternal and child mortality through better nutrition, child rearing practices, health care and prevention against diseases. And they will be assist their participation educationally, politically, socially and technologically in the society.

The woman companions of the Prophet were very hardworking; preliminary Hazrat Khadija (RA) who prepared a lot of sacrifice to support the Prophet in the propagation of the message of Islam, to Hazrat Ayesha (RA) who was erudite, up to the woman companions who addressed from family to family spreading the message of Islam, secretly and openly, and those who contributed enthusiastically in the religious battles were very meticulous and educated.

Muslim Female parents are now compounded with positive attitude towards girl child education not just like before where they are reluctant to send the girl-child for formal education. They now need equal access to good schooling as they are educationally backward. Bear almost all responsibility for meeting basic needs of the family, yet are systematically denied the resources, information and freedom of action they need to full fill this responsibility. The Girl must rise up to the challenges of the contemporary period. She should be an active contributor in the community development as done by the honourable womenfolk in the history of Islam. She should not just acquire the education, but must be seen to put the education acquired into full use.

Conclusion

It can conclude that Islam not only give a virtuous place of women in Islam, but also give her equal right as men; for betterment of the society. Girl education is the necessity of Muslim community for the development of the nation. She is the upcoming mentor of the nation builders and community developer. Muslim should change misconceptions regarding education, an educated woman is very well conscious regarding their rights and duties. The Muslim female should transformation her laziness towards achievement of education. The government specifically should take serious and attention of the Girl and the womenfolk in the educational planning, policy and practice for the women development and give them equal opportunities. The message of the paper is that Islam promotes education, particularly women education. But, we need to recognize the authenticity of the fundamental teachings of the Qur'an. The necessity and importance of the Girl education to the Muslim community and its development are enormous as she is the future trainer of the nation builders, the home managers and community developer. She plays vital roles in the development of the society. The female form more than half of the population. Neglecting their education, therefore, is neglecting development of more than half of the community. The male and female are created in order to complement one another. There is the need for the Muslim communities to avail their females the opportunity to acquire education to whatever level. The Muslims should change their belief and conception that female education to certain level is anti-religious, as this is completely erroneous. The Muslim female should change her apathy towards acquisition of education. The government especially the government of the states should take serious and care of the Girl and the woman folk in the educational planning, policy and practice and provide appropriate education to them. The government of the states should set in motion the effort to build female universities that will be conducive for learning by the females. This will not only comply with the religious requirement but will also encourage a number of the females to get themselves educated thereby redressing the present low percentage of the female educated women.

References

1. <https://www.academia.edu/3412941>
2. Al Qur'an 16: 58.
3. Zoya Hasan and Ritu Menon, Unequal citizens, Oxford University Press. New Delhi, 2004, p. 3.
4. The Qur'an 4:1.
5. Tahseen Ullha khan, Women's Right in Islam, Pakistan 2004, p.10.
6. Ibid.
7. Naseem Ahmad ,Women in Islam, vol 1, A.P.H Publishing Corporation New Delhi, 2003. p.90.
8. Hadith, English, reference; Ibn Majjha Vol, 1, Book 1, Hadith 224.
9. Rohani Hashim (ed.), Reclaiming the Conversion: Islamic Intellectual Tradition in the Malay Archipelago, The other press, Kuala Lumpur, 2010, p.3.
10. Tirmizi, 1980, Hadith - 1916.
11. Ibn Majah, 1952.